

HARIMALALA Mireille

Nom : HARIMALALA

Prénoms : Mireille A.

Date de naissance : 21 Octobre 1984

Poste actuelle : Chargée de recherche (CR3), Unité d'Entomologie Médicale, Institut Pasteur de Madagascar

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DIPLOMES

Docteur en Biologie Moléculaire (2012), Université de La Réunion, France

Master en Phytovirologie (2009), Université d'Antananarivo, Madagascar

Licence en Sciences Naturelles (2005), Université d'Antananarivo, Madagascar

EXPERIENCES PROFESSIONNELLES

Janvier 2020-Présent : Chargée de recherche

Avril 2016 – Décembre 2019 : Assistante de Recherche

Mars 2014 – Mars 2016 : Stagiaire de Recherche

PUBLICATIONS

Harimalala M, Rakotobe Harimanana R, Azali Hamza A, Girod R. Surveillance of fleas and their small mammal hosts for plague risks in some main seaports of the islands of the Southwestern Indian Ocean. *American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*, 2024, 110(2) : 311-319.

Rasoamalala F, Gostic K, Parany M J, Rahelinirina S, Rahajandraibe S, Gorgé O, Valade E, Harimalala M*, Rajerison M*, Ramasindrazana B*. Population dynamics of plague vector fleas in an endemic focus: implications for plague surveillance. *Journal of Medical Entomology*, 2024, 61(1) : 201-211.

Hutton S M, Miarinjara A, Stone N E, Raharimalala F N, Raveloson A O, Rakotobe Harimanana R, Harimalala M, Rahelinirina S, McDonough R F, Ames A D, Hepp C, Rajerison M, Busch J D, Wagner D M, Girod R. Knockdown resistance mutations are common and widely distributed in *Xenopsylla cheopis* fleas that transmit plague in Madagascar. *PLoS Neglected Tropical Diseases*, 2023, 17(8) : 1-25.

Rahelinirina S*, Harimalala M*, Rakotoniaina J, Randriamanantsoa MG, Dentinger C, Zohdy S, Girod R**, Rajerison M**. Tracking of mammals and their fleas for plague surveillance in Madagascar, 2018-2019. *American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*, 2022, 106(6) :1601-1609.

Duchemin J-B, Harimalala M, Duplantier J-M. Siphonaptera, fleas, parasy gasy. In *The New natural history of Madagascar*. Goodman S M (ed.), 2022, Princeton University Press, 2296p.

Harimalala M, Ramihangihajason TR, Rakotobe Harimanana R, Girod R, Duchemin J-B. Illustrated morphological keys of fleas (Siphonaptera) in Madagascar. *Journal of Medical Entomology*, 2021, 58(4), 1701-1716.

Harimalala M, Rahelinirina S, Girod R. Presence of the Oriental rat flea infesting an endemic mammal and confirmed plague circulation in a forest area of Madagascar. *Journal of Medical Entomology*, 2020, 57(4): 1318-1323.

Rahelinirina S, Harimalala M, Margueron T, Ramihangihajason TR, Mansotte F, Rajerison M, Pagès F, Boyer S. Risk of maritime introduction of plague from Madagascar to Mayotte. *Acta Tropica*, 2018, 187:140-143.

Harimalala M, Miarinjara A, Duchemin J-B, Ramihangihajason TR, Boyer S. Species diversity and phylogeny of fleas of small terrestrial mammals in the forests of the Central Highlands of Madagascar. *Zootaxa*, 2018, 4399 (2): 181–196.

- Harimalala M, Telfer S, Delatte H, Watts PC, Miarinjara A, Ramihangihajason TR, Rahelinirina S, Rajerison M, Boyer S. Genetic structure and gene flow of the flea *Xenopsylla cheopis* in Madagascar and Mayotte. *Parasites and Vectors*, 2017, 10:347.
- De Bruyn A, Harimalala M, Zinga I, Mabvakure B, Hoareau M, Ravigné V, Walters M, Reynaud B, Varsani A, Harkins GW, Martin DP, Lett J-M, Lefeuvre P. Divergent evolutionary and epidemiological dynamics of Cassava Mosaic Geminiviruses in Madagascar. *BMC Evolutionary Biology*, 2016, 16(182).
- Miarinjara A, Rogier C, Harimalala M, Ramihangihajason TR, Boyer S. *Xenopsylla brasiliensis* fleas in plague focus areas, Madagascar. *Emerging Infectious Diseases*, 2016, 22 (12): 2207-2208.
- Zinga I, Chiroleu F, Zango A V, Ballot CSA, Harimalala M, Komba E K, Yandia PS, Semballa S, Reynaud B, Lefeuvre P, Lett J-M, Dintinger J. Evaluation of cassava cultivars for resistance to Cassava Mosaic Disease and yield potential in Central African Republic. *Journal of Phytopathology*, 2016, 164: 913-923.
- De Bruyn A, Harimalala M, Hoareau M, Ranomenjanahary S, Reynaud B, Lefeuvre P, Lett J-M. Asystasia mosaic Madagascar virus : a novel bipartite begomovirus infecting the weed *Asystasia gangetica* in Madagascar. *Archives of Virology*, 2015, 160: 1589-1591.
- Harimalala M, Chiroleu F, Giraud-Carrier C, Hoareau M, Andriamampianina A, Velombola S, Ranomenjanahary S, Andrianjaka A, Reynaud B, Lefeuvre P, Lett J-M. Molecular epidemiology of cassava mosaic disease in Madagascar. *Plant Pathology*, 2014, 64(3): 501-507.
- Zinga I, Chiroleu F, Kamba E, Giraud-Carrier C, Harimalala M, Komba E, Yandia S, Semballa S, Reynaud B, Lefeuvre P, Dintinger J, Lett J-M. Field evaluation of effectiveness of thermotherapy against cassava mosaic disease in Central African Republic. *American Journal of Experimental Agriculture*, 2014, 4(11): 1232-1241.
- Harimalala M, De Bruyn A, Hoareau M, Andrianjaka A, Ranomenjanahary S, Reynaud B, Lefeuvre P, Lett J-M. Molecular characterization of a new alphasatellite associated with cassava mosaic geminivirus in Madagascar. *Archives of Virology*, 2013, 158(8): 1829-1832.
- Harimalala M, Lefeuvre P, De Bruyn A, Tiendrébéogo F, Hoareau M, Villemot J, Ranomenjanahary S, Andrianjaka A, Reynaud B, Lett J-M. A novel cassava-infecting begomovirus from Madagascar: cassava mosaic Madagascar virus. *Archives of Virology*, 2012, 157 : 2027-2030.
- Tiendrébéogo F, Lefeuvre P, Hoareau M, Harimalala M, De Bruyn A, Villemot J, Traoré V, Konaté G, Traoré A, Barro N, Reynaud B, Traoré O, Lett J-M. Evolution of *African cassava mosaic virus* by recombination between bipartite and monopartite begomoviruses. *Virology Journal*, 2012, 9: 67.
- Zinga I, Harimalala M, De Bruyn A, Hoareau M, Mandakombo N, Semballa S, Reynaud B, Lefeuvre P, Lett J-M. *East African cassava mosaic virus-Uganda* (EACMV-UG) and *African cassava mosaic virus* (ACMV) reported for the first time in Central African Republic and Chad. *New Disease Report*, 2012, 26:17.
- De Bruyn A, Villemot J, Lefeuvre P, Villar E, Hoareau M, Harimalala M, Abdoul-Karime A, Abdou-Chakour C, Reynaud B, Harkins G, Varsani A, Martin D, Lett J-M. East African cassava mosaic-like viruses from Africa to Indian Ocean islands: molecular diversity, evolutionary history and geographical dissemination of a bipartite begomovirus. *BMC Evolutionary Biology*, 2012, 12: 228.

RAJERISON Minoarisoa

Personal information

Name : RAJERISON Minoarisoa Esther

Birth : December 1st, 1971 **Nationality :** Malagasy

Personal address

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Professional address

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Professional Interests. I have been the head of the Plague Research Unit at IPM since 2011. In this capacity, I'm charged with investigating human plague epidemics within the country of Madagascar, from some plague endemic countries in African region and in the world (as a WHO Collaborating Center). I and my staff conduct plague cases confirmation, ATB surveillance of all isolated strains, rapid test production and research on *Yersinia pestis* and all actors of its transmission cycle (study in field, laboratory, and clinical settings). Our researches are focus on the question why plague remained endemic in Madagascar ? by investigating the human responses, the other plague cycle actor and the environment, ecology and epidemiology.

Skills

Research on Microbiology (Plague, Cholera, Leptospirosis), Immunology, immuno-diagnostic, epidemiology

Diagnostic tools development and evaluation (ELISA, Rapid test based on immunochromatography)

Management of 1 to 2 units with ~20 staffs ; conduct and management of several projects at the same time

Organisation of events/courses at national, regional and international levels (>200 participants)

Lab quality assessment : Auditor

Advisors : MoH and WHO

Education

2022 HDR-Ecole Doctorale Science de la Vie et de l'Environnement, Université d'Antananarivo « Contribution to improving the understanding of plague epidemiology and the plague control methods »

2003 PhD, Biochemical applied to Medical Sciences, Faculté des Sciences, Antananarivo-Madagascar « Development of RDT for the detection of cholera *Vibrio cholerae* O :1 toxin»

1999 Master2, Faculté des Sciences, Antananarivo-Madagascar « Dog as marker for plague : Development of ELISA for the detection of plague antibody from dogs»

1990 Baccalauréat Scientific, Madagascar

Courses and training

Dec-Jan 2007 : « Relevant courses on Management and Leadership » Institut National des Sciences Comptables et de l'Administration d'Entreprises INSCAE, Antananarivo

NOv-Déc 2005: « Relevant courses on Control Quality Assessment », Chambre de Commerce et de l'Industrie - La Réunion
Janv-Fev 2010 : Courses on “Biochimie des protéines”, Institut Pasteur à Paris (IPP)
Sept-Nov 2011: Courses on Microbiology, Institut Pasteur à Paris
Fév-mars 2013 : Courses on « Pathogens circulation and management of risk » IPP
2013-2014 : Courses CESAM statistic (module EPISUP) : Université Pierre et Marie-Curie
Sept 2018 : 9th Advanced course on diagnostics », Fondation Mérieux et London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine. Veyrier-du-Lac-France.

Work history

2011-current : **Institut Pasteur de Madagascar**
Head of the Plague -Researcher (Research Director-2)
Responsible WHO Collaborating Centre for the control and research on plague
External quality assessment of lab in the african region (EQA-WHO) : Rerefence Member of Rapid Response team of WHO and GOARN
Responsible of activities related to public health : lab confirmation, investigation, RDT production
Training and courses organisation : 5 regional or international courses organisation, 1 international symposium organisation-Chair

2004-2011 **Institut Pasteur de Madagascar**
Deputy Head of the Plague Unit-Responsible of Lab quality implementation

Sept 2010 **WHO and MoH** : Training on plague diagnosis, courses for the african region : Focal point and organizer.

August 2010 **WHO-PAHO** (PanAmerican Health Organisation) : temporary advisor during plague outbreak in Peru

Nov 2008 **WHO** : Temporary Advisors on External Quality Control of lab in African region

2004 (Oct-Nov) : **Institut Pasteur Paris** - Plate-Forme de Production de Protéines Recombinantes et d'anticorps : Training on the production of Monoclonal antibodies and development of RDT based on immunohromatography.

Publications (since 2021)

1. Andrianaivoarimanana V, Savin C, Birdsell DN, Vogler A J, Le Guern AS, Rahajandraibe S, Brémont S, Rahelinirina S, Sahl J W, Ramasindrazana B, Rakotonanahary R J-L, Rakotomanana F, Rendremanana R, Maheriniaina V, Razafimbiana V, Kwasiborski A, Balière C, Ratsitorahina M, Baril L, Keim P, Caro V, Rasolofo V, Spiegel A, Pizarro-Cerda J, Wagner D M, **Rajerison M**. Multiple independent introductions of *Yersinia pestis* from rural foci during 2017 urban pneumonic plague epidemic in Madagascar. *Emerg Infect Dis*. 2024;30(2):289-298. <https://doi.org/10.3201/eid3002.23075930>.
2. Shattock RJ, Andrianaivoarimanana V, McKay PF, Randriantseheno LN, Murugaiah V, Samnuan K, Rogers P, Tregoning JS, **Rajerison M**, Moore KM, Laws TR, Williamson ED. A self-amplifying RNA vaccine provides protection in a murine model of bubonic plague. *Front Microbiol*. 2023;14:1247041. doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2023.1247041.
3. Rahelinirina S, Rahajandraibe S, Rakotosamimanana S, **Rajerison M**. Assessing the effectiveness of intervention to prevent plague through community and animal-based survey. *PLOS Glob Public Health*. 2023;3(12):e0002211. doi: 10.1371/journal.pgph.0002211.
4. Hutton SM, Miarinjara A, Stone NE, Raharimalala FN, Raveloson AO, Harimanana RR, Harimalala M, Rahelinirina S, McDonough RF, Ames AD, Hepp C, **Rajerison M**, Busch JD, Wagner DM, Girod R. Knockdown resistance mutations are common and widely distributed in *Xenopsylla cheopis* fleas that transmit plague in Madagascar. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis*. 2023;17(8):e0011401. doi: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0011401.

5. Gomez LRE, Savin C, Andrianaivoarimanana V, Rahajandraibe S, Randriantseheno LN, Zhou Z, Kocher A, Didelot X, **Rajerison M**, Kühnert D. Phylogenetic analysis of the origin and spread of plague in Madagascar.
 - a. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis.* 2023;17(5):e0010362. doi: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0010362.
6. Rasoamalala F, Gostic K, Parany MJ, Rahelinirina S, Rahajandraibe S, Gorgé O, Valade E, Harimalala M*, **Rajerison M***, Ramasindrazana B*. Population dynamics of plague vector fleas in an endemic focus: implications for plague surveillance. *J Med Entomol.* 2023;tjad152. doi: 10.1093/jme/tjad152.
7. Scobie K, Rahelinirina S, Soarimalala V, Andriamiarimanana FM, Rahaingosoamamitiana C, Randriamoria T, Rahajandraibe S, Lambin X, **Rajerison M**, Telfer S. Reproductive ecology of the black rat (*Rattus rattus*) in Madagascar: the influence of density-dependent and -independent effects. *Integr Zool.* 2023;0: 1–21. doi: 10.1111/1749-4877.12750.
8. Rakotosamimanana S, Taglioni F, Ravaoarimanga M, **Rajerison ME**, Rakotomanana F. Socioenvironmental determinants as indicators of plague risk in the central highlands of Madagascar: Experience of Ambositra and Tsiroanomandidy districts. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis.* 2023;17(9):e0011538. doi: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0011538.
9. Bosch QT, Andrianaivoarimanana V, Ramasindrazana B, Mikaty G, Rakotonanahary RJJ, Nikolay B, Rahajandraibe S, Feher M, Grassin Q, Paireau J, Rahelinirina S, Randremanana R, Rakotoarimanana F, Melocco M, Rasolofo V, Pizarro-Cerda J, Le Guern AS, Bertherat E, Ratsitorahina M, Spiegel A, Baril L, **Rajerison M**, Cauchemez S. Analytical framework to evaluate and optimize the use of imperfect diagnostics to inform outbreak response: Application to the 2017 plague epidemic in Madagascar. *PLoS Biol.* 2022;20(8): e3001736. doi: 10.1371/journal.pbio.3001736.
10. Esmaeili S, Mahmoudi A, Esmaeili P, Ghalejoogh ZY, Mordadi A, Ghasemi A, Mohammadi A, Bagheri A, Sohrabi A, Latifian M, Rajerison M, Pizarro-Cerda J, Mostafavi E. The surveillance of plague among rodents and dogs in Western Iran. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis.* 2023;17(11):e0011722. doi: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0011722.
11. Rakotondrasoa A, Andrianonimiadana LM, Rahajandraibe S, Razafimahatratra S, Andrianaivoarimanana V, Rahelinirina S, Crucitti T, Brisse S, Jeannoda V, Rajerison M, Collard JM. Characterization of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolated from patients suspected of pulmonary or bubonic plague during the Madagascar epidemic in 2017. *Sci Rep.* 2022;12(1):6871. doi: 10.1038/s41598-022-10799-4.
12. Rasoamalala F, Parany MNJ, Rahanjandraibe S, Rakotomanga MN, Ramihangihajason T, Soarimalala V, Boyer S, Rajerison M, Ramasindrazana B. High rickettsial diversity in rodents and their ectoparasites from the Central Highlands of Madagascar. *J Med Entomol.* 2022;59(2):667-674. doi: 10.1093/jme/tjab207.
13. Ramasindrazana B, Parany MNJ, Rasoamalala F, Rasoanoro M, Rahajandraibe S, Vogler AJ, Sahl JW, Andrianaivoarimanana V, Rajerison M, Wagner DM. Local-scale diversity of *Yersinia pestis*: A case study from Ambohitromby, Ankazobe District, Madagascar. *Zoonoses Public Health.* 2022;69(1):61-70. doi: 10.1111/zph.12892.
14. Haikukutu L, Lyaku JR, Lyimo C, Kasanga CJ, Kandusi SE, Rahelinirina S, Rasoamalala F, Rajerison M, Makundi R. Plague in Tanzania: first report of sylvatic plague in Morogoro region, persistence in Mbulu focus, and going quiescence in Lushoto and Iringa foci. *IJID Reg.* 2022;4:105-110. doi: 10.1016/j.ijregi.2022.06.006.
15. Kaiser BLD, Birdsell DN, Hutchison JR, Thelaus J, Jenson SC, Andrianaivoarimanana V, Byström M, Myrtenäs K, McDonough R, Nottingham RD, Sahl JW, Schweizer HP, Rajerison M, Forsman M, Wunschel DS, Wagner DM. Proteomic signatures of antimicrobial resistance in *Yersinia pestis* and *Francisella tularensis*. *Front Med (Lausanne).* 2022;9:821071. doi: 10.3389/fmed.2022.821071.

16. Razafiarimanga ZN, Kouakou Yao YB, Rajerison M, Randriamampianina LV, Rahelinirina S, Rakotoarison R, Bastaroud A, Elisoa H, Handshumacher P, Jambou R. Risk factors for intestinal parasite portage in an informal suburb on the West coast of Madagascar. *Parasite Epidemiol Control*. 2022;19:e00267.doi: 10.1016/j.parepi.2022.e00267.
17. Rahelinirina S, Harimalala M, Rakotoniaina J, Randriamanantsoa MG, Dentinger C, Zohdy S, Girod R, Rajerison M. Tracking of Mammals and Their Fleas for Plague Surveillance in Madagascar, 2018-2019. *Am J Trop Med Hyg*. 2022;106(6):1601-1609. doi: 10.4269/ajtmh.21-0974. IF: 3,707.
18. Andrianaivoarimanana V, Wagner DM, Birdsell DN, Nikolay B, Rakotoarimanana F, Randriantseheno LN, Vogler AJ, Sahl JW, Hall CM, Somprasong N, Cauchemez S, Schweizer HP, Razafimandimby H, Rogier C, **Rajerison M**. Transmission of antimicrobial resistant *Yersinia pestis* during a pneumonic plague outbreak. *Clin Infect Dis*. 2022;74(4):695-702. doi: 10.1093/cid/ciab606.
19. V Andrianaivoarimanana, LN Randriantseheno, KM. Moore, NJ. Walker, SG Lonsdale, S Kempster, NA Almond, **M Rajerison** and ED Williamson. Potential human immunotherapeutics for plague. *Immunotherapy Advances*, 2021, Vol. 1, No. 1, 1–8 ; <https://doi.org/10.1093/immadv/ltab020>.
20. V Andrianaivoarimanana, DM. Wagner, DN. Birdsell, B Nikolay, F Rakotoarimanana, L N. Randriantseheno, AJ. Vogler, JW. Sahl, CM. Hall, N Somprasong, S Cauchemez, HP. Schweizer, H Razafimandimby, C Rogier and **M Rajerison**. Transmission of antimicrobial resistant *Yersinia pestis* during a pneumonic plague outbreak. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*, 2021. DOI [10.1093/cid/ciab606](https://doi.org/10.1093/cid/ciab606).
21. Aftalion M, Aloni-Grinstein R, Andrianaivoarimanana V, Lantoniaina Iharisoa A, Shmaya S, Gur D, Laskar O, **Rajerison M**, Mamroud E. Improved selective BIN agar for a better rate of *Yersinia pestis* isolation from primary clinical specimens in suspected Madagascar's plague cases. *J Clin Microbiol*. 2021 May 12: JCM.00564-21.2021; <https://doi.org/10.1128/JCM.00564-21>.
22. Rakotosamimanana S, Kassie D, Taglioni F, Ramamonjisoa J, Rakotomanana F and **Rajerison M**. A decade of plague in Madagascar: a description of two hotspot districts. *BMC Public Health*. 2021 Jun 10;21(1):1112. doi: 10.1186/s12889-021-11061-8. PMID: 34112118.
23. **M Rajerison**, M Ratsitorahina, V Andrianaivoarimanana, S Rahelinirina, S Chanteau, S Telfer, L Rahalison. Field assessment of dog as plague sentinel in endemic foci of Madagascar. *Integrative Zoology* 2021; 0: 1–7. doi: 10.1111/1749-4877.12541.
24. S Rahelinirina, K Scobie, B Ramasindrazana, V Andrianaivoarimanana, F Rasoamalala, LN Randriantseheno, JS Rakotoniaina, O Gorgé, X Lambin, E Valade, S Telfer, **M Rajerison**. Rodent control to fight plague: field assessment of methods based on rat density reduction. *Integrative Zoology* 2021; 0: 1–18. doi: 10.1111/1749-4877.12529.

I. CURRICULUM VITAE

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Formations académiques

2024 : HDR, Ecole Doctorale Sciences de la vie et de l'Environnement « Compréhension et gestion de risque de maladies zoonotiques transmises par les rongeurs »

2009 : Docteur en Sciences de la vie, Spécialité Biologie, Ecologie et Conservation Animales
Faculté des Sciences, Université d'Antananarivo, Madagascar.

Titre : « Risque pesteux dans les foyers ruraux du Moyen Ouest malgache : déplacements et structuration des populations de rats noirs *Rattus rattus* (Linnaeus, 1758) de l'échelle de l'habitat à celle du paysage »

1998 : DEA Option Ecologie et Environnement

Faculté des Sciences, Université d'Antananarivo, Madagascar.

Titre : « Etude préliminaire de la dynamique des réservoirs et vecteurs de la peste sur les Hauts Plateaux : suivi mensuel du rat noir (*Rattus rattus* L., 1757) et de ses puces (*Xenopsylla cheopis* Rothschild, 1903 et *Synopsyllus fonquerniei* Wagner et Roubaud, 1932) durant une année dans le Moyen Ouest »

Expériences professionnelles

Depuis 2020 : Chargée de Recherche, Unité Peste, Institut Pasteur de Madagascar

2014 – 2019 : Assistante de Recherche, Unité Peste, Institut Pasteur de Madagascar

Depuis 2009 : Cadre scientifique mammalogiste, Unité Peste, Institut Pasteur de Madagascar

Novembre – décembre 2022 : Mobilité de recherche au CBGP : Métagénomique bactérien 16S

Mai – août 2019 : Mobilité de recherche au Sokoine University of Agriculture, Morogoro, Tanzanie (bourse AAS Ishango) : Contrôle de fertilité de rats noirs

Août 2010 : Consultances CCOMS au Pérou (15 jours): Surveillance et contrôle des rongeurs réservoirs de la peste

Cours et Formations

Décembre 2023 : Conception Procédure animale CYROI La Réunion

2015 - 2016 : Cours sur les méthodes statistiques en Santé, Institut de Santé Publique d'Epidémiologie et de Développement, Université de Bordeaux, France

Mai 2015 : Formation sur les animaux de laboratoire en recherche biomédicale, Institut Pasteur Hellénique, Grèce

Août 2011 : Formation sur les diagnostics de la leptospirose, Centre Hospitalier Sud Réunion, Saint-Pierre, La Réunion

Juin 2011 : Formation en Expérimentation animale niveau 1, Université Claude Bernard, Lyon 1, France

Mai 2010 : Cours international sur les Zoonoses, Institut Pasteur Paris, France

Mai – août 2007 : Formation sur la génétique de population de rats, Centre de Biologie et Gestion des Populations (CBGP), Montpellier, France

Janvier 2006 : Formation sur l'utilisation de bio marqueurs fluorescents Rhodamine B sur les rongeurs, Institut de Recherche pour le Développement, Bamako, Mali

Autres activités :

Depuis 2013: Membre du Comité Consultatif d'Hygiène et Sécurité, Institut Pasteur de Madagascar

Depuis 2013 : Membre du Comité d'Ethique Animale de l'Institut Pasteur de Madagascar

Depuis 2014 : Membre de l'Equipe d'Accueil « Immunologie, Immunodiagnostic et Immunohistologie (3I) » de l'Ecole Doctorale Sciences de la Vie et de l'Environnement (ED SVE) - Université d'Antananarivo

Publication (depuis 2021)

1. Andrianaivoarimanana V, Savin C, Birdsell DN, Vogler A J, Le Guern AS, Rahajandraibe S, Brémont S, **Rahelinirina S**, Sahl J W, Ramasindrazana B, Rakotonanahary R J-L, Rakotomanana F, Rendremanana R, Maheriniaina V, Razafimbiana V, Kwasiborski A, Balière C, Ratsitorahina M, Baril L, Keim P, Caro V, Rasolofo V, Spiegel A, Pizarro-Cerda J, Wagner D M, Rajerison M. Multiple independent introductions of *Yersinia pestis* from rural foci during 2017 urban pneumonic plague epidemic in Madagascar. *Emerg Infect Dis.* 2024;30(2):289-298. <https://doi.org/10.3201/eid3002.23075930>.

2. **Rahelinirina S**, Rahajandraibe S, Rakotosamimanana S, Rajerison M. Assessing the effectiveness of intervention to prevent plague through community and animal-based survey. *PLOS Glob Public Health*. 2023;3(12):e0002211. doi: 10.1371/journal.pgph.0002211.
3. Hutton SM, Miarinjara A, Stone NE, Raharimalala FN, Raveloson AO, Harimanana RR, Harimalala M, **Rahelinirina S**, McDonough RF, Ames AD, Hepp C, Rajerison M, Busch JD, Wagner DM, Girod R. Knockdown resistance mutations are common and widely distributed in *Xenopsylla cheopis* fleas that transmit plague in Madagascar. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis*. 2023;17(8):e0011401. doi: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0011401.
4. Rasoamalala F, Gostic K, Parany MJ, **Rahelinirina S**, Rahajandraibe S, Gorgé O, Valade E, Harimalala M*, Rajerison M*, Ramasindrazana B*. Population dynamics of plague vector fleas in an endemic focus: implications for plague surveillance. *J Med Entomol*. 2023:tjad152. doi: 10.1093/jme/tjad152.
5. Scobie K, **Rahelinirina S**, Soarimalala V, Andriamiarimanana FM, Rahaingosoamamitiana C, Randriamoria T, Rahajandraibe S, Lambin X, Rajerison M, Telfer S. Reproductive ecology of the black rat (*Rattus rattus*) in Madagascar: the influence of density-dependent and -independent effects. *Integr Zool*. 2023;0: 1–21. doi: 10.1111/1749-4877.12750.
6. **Rahelinirina S**, Harimalala M, Rakotoniaina J, Randriamanantsoa MG, Dentinger C, Zohdy S, Girod R, Rajerison M. Tracking of mammals and their fleas for plague surveillance in Madagascar, 2018-2019. *American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene* 2022 ; 106(6):1601-1609. doi: 10.4269/ajtmh.21-0974
7. Haikukutu L, Lyaku JR, Lyimo C, Kasanga CJ, Kandusi SE, **Rahelinirina S**, Rasoamalala F, Rajerison M, Makundi R. Plague in Tanzania: first report of sylvatic plague in Morogoro region, persistence in Mbulu focus, and ongoing quiescence in Lushoto and Iringa foci. *International Journal of Infectious Diseases Regions*. 2022 ;4: 105-110 doi: 10.1016/j.ijregi.2022.06.006
8. Rakotondrasoa A, Andrianonimiadana LM, Rahajandraibe S, Razafimahatratra S, Andrianaivoarimanana V, **Rahelinirina S**, Crucitti T, Brisse S, Jeannoda V, Rajerison M, Collar J-M. Characterization of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolated from patients suspected of pulmonary or bubonic plague during the Madagascar epidemic in 2017. *Scientific Reports* 2022 ; 12 (1). doi : 10.1038/s41598-022-10799-4
9. Razafiarimanga ZN, Yao YBK, Rajerison M, Randriamampianina LJ, **Rahelinirina S**, Rakotoarison R, Bastarud A, Hariniaina E, Handscumacher P, Ronan J. Risk factors for intestinal parasite portage in an informal suburb on the west coast of Madagascar. *Parasite Epidemiology and Control* 2022 ; 19. doi : 10.1016/j.parepi.2022.e00267
10. Bosch QT, Andrianaivoarimanana V, Ramasondravana B, Mikaty G, Rakotonanahary RJL, Nikolay B, Rahajandraibe S, Feher M, Grassin Q, Paireau J, **Rahelinirina S**, Rendremanana R, Rakotoarimanana F, Melocco M, Rasolofo V, Pizarro-Cerda J, Le Guern A-S, Bertherat E, Ratsitorahina M, Spoegel A, Baril L, Rajerison M, Cauchemez S. Analytical framework to evaluate and optimize the use of imperfect diagnostics to inform outbreak response: Application to the 2017 plague epidemic in Madagascar. *PLOS Biology*. 2022 ; 20(8). doi: 10.1371/journal.pbio.3001736.
11. **Rahelinirina S**, Scobie K, Ramasindrazana B, Andrianaivoarimanana V, Rasoamalala F, Randriantseheno LN, Rakotoniaina JS, Gorgé O, Lambin X, Valade V, Telfer S, Rajerison M. Rodent control to fight plague: field assessment of methods based on rat density reduction. *Integrative Zoology*. 2021; 16(6):868-885. doi: 10.1111/1749-4877.12529

12. Rajerison M, Ratsitorahina M, Andrianaivoarimanana V, **Rahelinirina S**, Chanteau S, Telfer S, Rahalison L Field assessment of dog as plague sentinel in endemic foci of Madagascar. *Integrative Zoology*. 2021; 16 : 886 - 892. doi: 10.1111/1749-4877.12541.

Chapitre d'ouvrage

1. Ramasindrazana B, Randriamoria TM, **Rahelinirina S**, Duchemin J-B, Duplantier J-M, Soarimalala V, Goodman SM. Introduced terrestrial small mammals. In Goodman S M, ed. *The new natural history of Madagascar*. Princeton, New Jersey: Princeton University Press.